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“MY JOURNEY FROM WATCHMAN TO EDUCATOR”

I have aspired to pursue electrical engineering from childhood. But because of my limited resources, I chose a more practicable path and enrolled in the Central Visayas Polytechnic College, which is now Negros Oriental State University, to study electrical technology.

I didn't have an easy time getting to college. At first, my father and I go in the wrong school a high school, not a college because we were not familiar with the city and the enrolling procedure. Finding the perfect school required us to visit two different ones. I was determined to persevere in spite of the difficult beginning.

I then pursued a Bachelor of Science in Industrial Education (BSIE) with a major in electrical technology and a minor in mathematics because I wanted to advance my knowledge. The journey was difficult, especially since we were without electricity at home, making it incredibly difficult for me to study. However, these challenges just underwired my will to succeed.

I took on leadership positions while I was in college. I furthered my leadership and discipline by serving as the president of the supreme student government and rising to the rank of Advance Officer in the Naval ROTC.

I took the Teacher Licensure Examination after finishing my course, and I passed. However, teaching wasn't the first step in my professional career. I started out at the same university as a watchman. I gained promotion gradually, first to an administrative assistant role in the University Registrar's Office and subsequently to the Human Resource Management Office.

Finally, an opportunity presented itself. I was promoted to a teaching position with an emphasis on electricity, which I had always appreciated.

Looking back, the trip was fraught with challenges and setbacks, but each one helped form the life I live now, one dedicated to inspiring the next generation, as I had always hoped.